

Studies on Stability Constants of Aluminium(III) and Thorium(IV) Complexes with Methionine [Metal(M)-Methionine System]

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Manuscript received 7 March 1996, revised 30 July 1997, accepted 12 August 1997

A significant development on the determination of stability constants of complexes was made by Jokl¹ and a theoretical treatment similar to that of Jokl was adopted by Biernat and Roczniki² for the study of stepwise complex formation. The use of paper electrophoretic technique for the study of metal complex system is reported in literature³. No reports on complexes of Al^{III} and Th^{IV} with methionine is available.

In view of this, attempts were made to find out the best conditions for metal(M)-methionine complex formation. The stability constants of these complexes were determined by electrophoretic method.

Results and Discussion

Metal-methionine binary system : The electrophoretic mobility of metal spot against a pH gives a curve with the number of plateaus shown in Fig. 1. The every plateau indicates the formation of certain complex species. A plateau is obviously an indication of a pH range, where speed is practically constant. The first one corresponds to a region where metal ions are uncomplexed. The second plateau in each case with positive mobility indicates 1 : 1 complexes of cationic nature. Further increase of pH, mobility in case

of Al^{III} metal ion decreases giving rise to a third plateau in positive region indicating 1 : 2 metal complex of cationic nature, while in case of Th^{IV} ion, mobility remains constant with increase of pH, indicating that only 1 : 1 complex is formed. Thus, the complexation of Al^{III} and Th^{IV} with methionine anion [L⁻] may be represented as

The metal spot on the paper is thus a conglomeration of uncomplexed metal ions (Al³⁺, Th⁴⁺), 1 : 1 [AlL]²⁺, (ThL)³⁺ complex and 1 : 2 [AlL₂]⁺ complex. For the spot moving under the influence of electric field, the overall mobility is given by the equation⁴,

$$U = \sum_n u_n f_n \quad (4)$$

Equation (4) is transformed into the following useful form on taking into consideration the different equilibria,

$$U = \frac{u_0 + u_1 K_1 [\text{L}^-] + u_2 K_1 K_2 [\text{L}^-]^2}{1 + K_1 [\text{L}^-] + K_1 K_2 [\text{L}^-]^2} \quad (5)$$

where, u_0 , u_1 and u_2 are mobility of uncomplexed metal ion, 1 : 1 metal complex and 1 : 2 metal complex respectively. Equation (5) has been used for calculating stability constants of complexes of the metal ions with methionine. For calculating K_1 , the region between the first and second plateau is pertinent. The overall mobility (U) will be equal to the arithmetic mean of mobilities of uncomplexed metal ions, u_0 and that of first complex, u_1 at a pH, where $K_1 = 1/[\text{L}^-]$.

With the help of protonation constants of methionine ($pK_1 = 2.25$, $pK_2 = 9.00$), the concentration of methionine anion is determined at the pH of average mobility from which K_1 can be calculated. The concentration of chelating amino acid (methionine) species [L⁻] is calculated with the help of the equation,

Fig. 1. Mobility curves for the M-methionine systems : (O) Al^{III}-methionine and (●) Th^{IV}-methionine.

$$[L^-] = \frac{[L_T]}{1 + \frac{[H]}{K_2} + \frac{[H]^2}{K_1 K_2}}$$

where, $[L_T]$ is the total concentration of ligand methionine, and K_1 and K_2 are the first and second dissociation constants of methionine. The stability constant K_2 of the second complex can be calculated by taking into consideration the region between second and third plateau of mobility curve.

The stability constants of different complex species were determined electrophoretically at an ionic strength of 0.1 M perchloric acid at 35°. The stability constants of ML and ML_2 complex species of Al^{III} - and Th^{IV} -methionine have been found to be $(7.00 \pm 0.02, 11.50 \pm 0.01)$ and $(8.08 \pm 0.05, -)$ respectively. It may be said that the amino acid methionine may be used to reduce the level of Al^{III} and Th^{IV} in biological systems.

Experimental

Methods were the same as described earlier³.

All the reagents used were of A.R. grade. Solutions of Al^{III} and Th^{IV} perchlorates were prepared by precipitating the metal carbonates from 0.1 M solution of sulphates

(6) or nitrates of the metal ions with solution of sodium carbonate.

Metal spots were detected on the paper using aluminon solution (B.D.H.) for Al^{III} , and 1-(2-pyridylazo)-2-naphthol for Th^{IV} . A saturated aqueous solution (0.9 M) of silver nitrate was diluted with acetone to 20 ml. Glucose as the black spot, was detected by spraying with this solution and then with 2% ethanolic NaOH. The background electrolytes used in the study of binary complexes were 0.1 M perchloric acid and 1.0×10^{-2} M methionine.

Acknowledgement

The author is grateful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for financial assistance.

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